

Performance Analysis of Fluid Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface over Covert Communications

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Abstract—This paper investigates the impact of the recently proposed concept of fluid reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (FRIS) on covert communications. Specifically, we consider a communication scenario where a legitimate transmitter aims to covertly deliver information to a legitimate receiver through a planar FRIS, while an adversary attempts to detect this hidden transmission. In this context, we analyze the false alarm (FA) and missed detection (MD) probabilities, and derive a closed-form expression for the covertness outage probability (COP). Furthermore, the success probability is characterized under the optimal detection threshold, providing new insights into the trade-off between covertness and reliable transmission. Numerical results reveal that FRIS provides a clear advantage over conventional RIS at low-to-moderate transmit powers by improving reliability and enhancing covertness, while at very high power levels, conventional RIS may sustain slightly higher success probability due to reduced leakage toward the adversary.

Index Terms—Fluid reconfigurable intelligent surface, covert communications, performance analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RISs) have been widely investigated as a low-cost and energy-efficient solution to reshape the wireless propagation environment by coherently controlling electromagnetic reflections through a large number of passive elements [1]. Despite their promise, conventional RISs suffer from two key limitations: *i*) the multiplicative path-loss effect due to the cascaded transmitter-RIS-receiver link, which often results in severe attenuation, and *ii*) their rigid geometry, which prevents effective exploitation of spatial diversity in environments where physical space is abundant [2].

To address these limitations, the concept of fluid reconfigurable intelligent surface (FRIS) [3] and fluid integrated reflecting and emitting surface (FIRES) [4] have recently emerged, inspired by the fluid antenna system (FAS) [5]–[8]. Unlike conventional RISs, where elements are fixed in position, FRIS enables position reconfigurability by allowing each reflecting element to dynamically switch its active port within a dense preset grid distributed across the surface. This quasi-continuous spatial reconfiguration provides additional degrees of freedom (DoFs) beyond phase control, enabling adaptive element selection, stronger constructive alignment toward intended receivers, and better suppression of undesired leakage. Early studies have demonstrated that FRIS achieves

substantial improvements in outage probability, secrecy rate, and spectral efficiency compared to conventional RIS [9]–[11]. These results highlight FRIS as a strong candidate for future wireless networks, where highly adaptive and robust communications are essential.

Meanwhile, covert communication has gained increasing attention as a new physical layer security (PLS) paradigm, aiming not only to protect information but also to conceal the very existence of transmission from an adversarial warden [12]–[14]. Covert techniques are particularly relevant in dense wireless environments, such as vehicular and Internet of Things (IoT) networks, where the risk of detection is high and conventional cryptographic or PLS approaches may be insufficient. Although RIS-assisted covert communications have been studied, the potential of FRIS in this context remains unexplored.

Motivated by this gap, this paper provides the first study of FRIS-aided covert communications. In this regard, we consider a covert communication system where a legitimate transmitter communicates with a legitimate receiver through a planar FRIS, while an adversary attempts to detect the transmission. For this model, we develop a tractable analytical framework to characterize the outage probability (OP), covertness outage probability (COP), and success probability, thereby capturing the fundamental trade-off between reliability and covertness. Closed-form expressions are derived using moment-matching techniques, which enable accurate characterization of the system behavior under FRIS reconfigurability. The analytical and numerical results consistently demonstrate that FRIS can significantly enhance covert communication performance compared to conventional RIS at low-to-moderate transmit powers, owing to its adaptive element-selection capability, while at very high power levels the performance gap between FRIS and RIS becomes less pronounced.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

A. Channel Model

We consider a wireless FRIS-assisted covert communication system as presented in 1, in which a legitimate transmitter (Alice) intends to covertly deliver information to a legitimate receiver (Bob) via a FRIS, while an adversary (Willie) attempts to detect the presence of the hidden transmission. For notation

Fig. 1. The considered FRIS-FRIS-aided covert communication.

simplicity, we use A , B , and W define Alice, Bob and Willie, respectively. All nodes are assumed to be equipped with a single fixed-position antenna, where the legitimate users operate in half-duplex mode, whereas the adversary operates in full-duplex mode. Furthermore, the direct communication links from Alice to both Bob and Willie are assumed to be blocked by obstacles. The considered FRIS consists of $M = M_x \times M_z$ reflective elements, each operating in one of two discrete states of ON or OFF, where M_x and M_z specify the element counts along the horizontal (x -axis) and vertical (z -axis) directions, respectively. In the ON state, an element interacts with the incident electromagnetic wave, thereby enabling the intended system functionality through wave manipulation. Conversely, in the OFF state, the element is terminated by a matched load, which suppresses interaction with the incoming signal and avoids any alteration of the wavefront. The reflecting elements are uniformly arranged over a planar aperture of size $W = W_x \lambda \times W_z \lambda$, where λ denotes the carrier wavelength, and W_x and W_z denote the corresponding aperture dimensions normalized to the wavelength.

FRIS elements are placed in close proximity, which necessitates accounting for spatial correlation among different element positions. To characterize this effect, the Jakes' model is employed to represent the correlation coefficient between any two elements i and j under rich scattering conditions, expressed as $\mu_{i,j} = \mathcal{J}_0\left(\frac{2\pi d_{i,j}}{\lambda}\right)$, where $\mathcal{J}_0(\cdot)$ is the zero-order Bessel function of the first kind and $d_{i,j}$ denotes the inter-element distance, i.e.,

$$d_{i,j} = \sqrt{d_x^2 (\widetilde{M}_i - \widetilde{M}_j)^2 + d_z^2 \left(\left\lfloor \frac{i}{M_x} \right\rfloor - \left\lfloor \frac{j}{M_x} \right\rfloor \right)^2}, \quad (1)$$

where $\widetilde{M}_i = \text{mod}(i, M_x)$, $\widetilde{M}_j = \text{mod}(j, M_x)$, and $d_x = \frac{W_x \lambda}{M_x}$ and $d_z = \frac{W_z \lambda}{M_z}$ denote the physical inter-element spacing in each FRIS row and column, respectively. Thus, the spatial correlation matrix is defined as $\mathbf{J} = [\mu_{i,j}]_{M \times M}$.

B. Covert Transmission Scheme and Detection Model

We consider that Alice adopts a power control (PC) strategy, where her transmit power P_A is carefully adjusted so that the information signals remain hidden within the background noise, thereby enhancing covertness. On the other side, Willie

employs a likelihood ratio test (LRT) [15] to identify potential transmissions. Specifically, he selects a decision threshold ζ and computes the average received power \overline{P}_A over the observation interval. A decision in favor of transmission, denoted by hypothesis \mathcal{H}_1 , is made if $\overline{P}_W \geq \zeta$, while the absence of transmission, denoted as \mathcal{H}_0 , is concluded if $\overline{P}_W < \zeta$. This decision rule can be compactly expressed as $\overline{P}_W \underset{\mathcal{H}_0}{\overset{\mathcal{H}_1}{\geq}} \zeta$.

The LRT may lead to two possible decision errors: *i*) false alarm (FA), where Willie incorrectly declares a transmission under \mathcal{H}_0 , and *ii*) missed detection (MD), where an actual transmission under \mathcal{H}_1 is overlooked. The probabilities of these events are denoted by p_{FA} and p_{MD} , respectively. When both errors are avoided, the communication is deemed covert, as Willie is unable to reliably infer Alice's activity.

C. Signal Model

When Alice is active, she transmits a vector of K symbols denoted by \mathbf{x} , where each entry $\mathbf{x}[k]$, $k = 1, \dots, K$, satisfies a unit-power constraint such that $\mathbb{E}|\mathbf{x}[k]|^2 = 1$. In contrast, when Alice remains silent, Willie only observes noise. Accordingly, assuming that M_O elements will be turned ON to modulate the incident signal, the received signal at Willie is expressed as

$$y_W[k] = \begin{cases} \sqrt{P_A L_{AF} L_{FW}} H_W \mathbf{x}[k] + n_W[k], & \mathcal{H}_1 \\ n_W[k], & \mathcal{H}_0 \end{cases}, \quad (2)$$

where $L_u = \rho_0 d_u^{-\alpha}$, for $u \in \{AF, FW\}$ indicates the large-scale path-loss in which ρ_0 is the reference gain at one meter, α is the path-loss exponent, and d_u denotes the distance of the corresponding links u . Additionally, $n_W[k] \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_W^2)$ are i.i.d. receiver noise samples and H_W denotes the end-to-end channel received at Willie through FRIS, which is given by

$$H_W = \mathbf{h}_{FW}^H \mathbf{J}^{\frac{1}{2}} \mathbf{S}_{M_O}^T \mathbf{\Phi} \mathbf{S}_{M_O} \mathbf{J}^{\frac{1}{2}} \mathbf{h}_{AF}, \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{h}_u \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ represents the small-scale fading for the Alice-to-FRIS or FRIS-to-Willie links, i.e., $\mathbf{h}_u \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \mathbf{I}_M)$. The diagonal matrix $\mathbf{\Phi} = \text{diag}\{e^{j\phi_1}, \dots, e^{j\phi_M}\} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times M}$ includes the adjustable phases of the reflecting elements of the FRIS and $\mathbf{S}_{M_O}^T = [\mathbf{s}_1, \dots, \mathbf{s}_{M_O}] \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times M_O}$ is the element selection matrix, in which \mathbf{s}_{m_O} , for $m_O \in M_O = \{1, \dots, M_O\}$, indicates one of the columns of the $M \times M$ identity matrix¹.

Therefore, for detection, Willie evaluates the average received power, given by

$$\overline{P}_W = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K |y_W[k]|^2 = \begin{cases} P_A L_{AF} L_{FW} g_W + \sigma_W^2, & \mathcal{H}_1 \\ \sigma_W^2, & \mathcal{H}_0 \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

where $g_W = |h_W|^2$ denotes the channel power gain. Equation (4) follows from the strong law of large numbers, applied to

¹In FRIS, only a subset of meta-elements is activated at a time. This behavior is modeled through the binary selection matrix \mathbf{S}_{M_O} , which projects the full aperture of size M onto M_O active elements while ensuring orthogonality. The model captures the fluid antenna principle, where the active elements are dynamically chosen to maximize channel gain, with ideal and fully controllable phase shifts assumed.

(2) as $K \rightarrow \infty$. This enables Willie to reliably estimate the received signal power and subsequently decide on the presence or absence of Alice's transmission by comparing it with the decision threshold.

III. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

In this section, we derive analytical expressions for the COP, OP, and success probability to evaluate the performance of the proposed FRIS-aided covert communication.

A. Covertess Outage Probability

COP characterizes the likelihood that Willie successfully detects Alice's activity. A covert outage occurs when neither a FA nor a MD event arises. Accordingly, the COP can be expressed as

$$P_{\text{CO}} = 1 - (P_{\text{FA}} + P_{\text{MD}}). \quad (5)$$

1) *Missed Detection Probability*: A missed detection event occurs when Alice transmits, yet Willie's detector fails to identify her activity. This happens whenever the observed average received power \bar{P}_W does not exceed the decision threshold ζ . The MD probability is thus given by

$$P_{\text{MD}} = \Pr(P_{\text{A}}L_{\text{AF}}L_{\text{FW}}g_W + \sigma_W^2 \leq \zeta) \quad (6)$$

$$= \Pr\left(g_W \leq \frac{\zeta - \sigma_W^2}{P_{\text{A}}L_{\text{AF}}L_{\text{FW}}}\right) \quad (7)$$

$$= F_{g_W}\left(\frac{\zeta - \sigma_W^2}{P_{\text{A}}L_{\text{AF}}L_{\text{FW}}}\right) \quad (8)$$

$$= \begin{cases} F_{g_W}(\eta), & \zeta > \sigma_W^2 \\ 0, & \zeta \leq \sigma_W^2 \end{cases}, \quad (9)$$

where $F_{g_W}(\eta)$ is the CDF of g_W in which $\eta = \frac{\zeta - \sigma_W^2}{P_{\text{A}}L_{\text{AF}}L_{\text{FW}}}$. The CDF of the channel gain at Willie g_W can be accurately approximated by the Gamma distribution via moment matching method [10, Lemma 1] as follows

$$F_{g_W}(g) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\kappa)} \Upsilon\left(\kappa, \frac{g}{\theta}\right), \quad (10)$$

where $\kappa = \frac{(\text{tr}(\tilde{\mathbf{J}}^2))^2}{\text{tr}(\tilde{\mathbf{J}}^4)}$, $\theta = \frac{\text{tr}(\tilde{\mathbf{J}}^4)}{\text{tr}(\tilde{\mathbf{J}}^2)}$, and $\tilde{\mathbf{J}} = \mathbf{S}_{\text{M}_O} \mathbf{J} \mathbf{S}_{\text{M}_O}^T$. Therefore, the probability of missed detection is derived as

$$P_{\text{MD}} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\kappa)} \Upsilon\left(\kappa, \frac{\eta}{\theta}\right), & \zeta > \sigma_W^2 \\ 0, & \zeta \leq \sigma_W^2 \end{cases}. \quad (11)$$

2) *False Alarm Probability*: A false alarm arises when Willie incorrectly infers the presence of a transmission under \mathcal{H}_0 . This occurs when $\bar{P}_W \geq \zeta$, which leads to

$$P_{\text{FA}} = \Pr(\sigma_W^2 \geq \zeta) = \begin{cases} 0, & \zeta > \sigma_W^2 \\ 1, & \zeta \leq \sigma_W^2 \end{cases}. \quad (12)$$

3) *Closed-Form COP Expression*: By combining (11) and (12) into (5), the COP is expressed as

$$P_{\text{CO}} = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\kappa)} \Upsilon\left(\kappa, \frac{\eta}{\theta}\right), & \zeta > \sigma_W^2 \\ 0, & \zeta \leq \sigma_W^2 \end{cases}. \quad (13)$$

In the FRIS-aided covert communication scenario, Willie seeks to maximize the COP, denoted as P_{CO} , by carefully selecting his detection threshold ζ . Recall that P_{COP} depends jointly on Willie's false alarm and missed detection probabilities, both of which are influenced by ζ . When $\zeta \leq \sigma_W^2$, the false alarm probability becomes one, which immediately forces $P_{\text{CO}} = 0$. Hence, any meaningful choice of threshold must lie in the region $\zeta > \sigma_W^2$. From the expression of the missed detection probability in (8), it is evident that as ζ increases, the argument of the CDF increases, and therefore $P_{\text{MD}}(\zeta)$ increases monotonically. Given COP is a decreasing function of the detection capability, maximizing P_{CO} requires Willie to minimize his overall detection capability. This occurs when ζ is chosen as close as possible to σ_W^2 , but strictly greater to avoid the trivial case. Thus, in the FRIS-aided model, the optimal threshold for Willie is characterized as

$$\zeta^* = \sigma_W^2 + \mu, \quad (14)$$

where $\mu > 0$ is an arbitrarily small positive constant. This selection ensures that Willie minimizes his decision statistic while respecting the feasibility condition $\zeta > \sigma_W^2$, thereby maximizing the covertess probability.

B. Outage Probability

In the considered FRIS-assisted covert communication, the OP quantifies the likelihood that Alice's transmission to Bob fails due to inadequate channel capacity. Formally, the OP is defined as $P_{\text{OUT}} = \Pr(C_B < R_B)$, where R_B is the target data rate and $C_B = \log_2(1 + \gamma_B)$ denotes the instantaneous channel capacity of the Alice to Bob link through FRIS in which γ_B is the SNR at Bob.

When Alice transmits with power P_A , the FRIS constructs an equivalent channel H_B towards Bob. The corresponding received SNR is given by

$$\gamma_B = \frac{P_{\text{A}}L_{\text{AF}}L_{\text{FB}}|\mathbf{h}_{\text{FB}}^H \mathbf{J}^{\frac{1}{2}} \mathbf{S}_{\text{M}_O}^T \Phi \mathbf{S}_{\text{M}_O} \mathbf{J}^{\frac{1}{2}} \mathbf{h}_{\text{AF}}|^2}{\sigma_B^2}, \quad (15)$$

where $L_{\text{FB}} = \rho_0 d_{\text{FB}}^{-\alpha}$ denotes the large-scale path-loss of the FRIS-to-Bob link and d_{FB} is the corresponding distance. The term \mathbf{h}_{FB} accounts the small-scale fading for the FRIS-to-Bob links, i.e., $\mathbf{h}_{\text{FB}} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \mathbf{I}_M)$.

Following the FRIS channel characterization, $g_B = |H_B|^2$ is well approximated by a Gamma distribution with shape parameter κ and scale parameter θ , $g_B \sim \text{Gamma}(\kappa, \theta)$. Thus, the OP is derived as

$$P_{\text{OUT}} = \Pr(\log_2(1 + \gamma_B) \leq R_B) \quad (16)$$

$$= F_{g_B}\left(\frac{(2^{R_B} - 1)\sigma_B^2}{P_{\text{A}}L_{\text{AF}}L_{\text{FB}}}\right) \quad (17)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\kappa)} \Upsilon\left(\kappa, \frac{\bar{R}}{\theta}\right), \quad (18)$$

Fig. 2. OP versus transmit power P_A for different number of fluid elements M_O .

where $F_{g_B}(g)$ denotes the CDF of the Gamma-distributed equivalent channel gain g_B and $\bar{R}_B = \frac{(2^{R_B} - 1)\sigma_B^2}{P_{ALAF}L_{FB}}$.

C. Success Probability

In FRIS-assisted covert communication, a fundamental trade-off arises between maintaining covertness against Willie and ensuring reliable transmission to Bob. A transmission is deemed successful only if two conditions are simultaneously satisfied: (i) Willie fails to detect Alice's activity, and (ii) the Alice-FRIS-Bob link supports the target data rate R_B . The level of covertness is governed by the detection threshold ζ , which directly influences Willie's missed detection probability, whereas reliability is determined by the equivalent FRIS-aided channel gain g_B at Bob. To jointly capture these effects, the success probability is defined as

$$P_{\text{SUC}} = P_{\text{MD}}(\zeta^*) \times (1 - P_{\text{OUT}}), \quad (19)$$

where $P_{\text{MD}}(\zeta^*)$ denotes the probability of missed detection under the optimal detection threshold ζ^* in (11), and P_{OUT} represents the OP of the Alice-FRIS-Bob channel in (18).

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, we present numerical results to evaluate the performance of the proposed FAS-aided covert communication system. Unless otherwise stated, the system parameters are set as $d_{AF} = 50$ m, $d_{FB} = d_{FW} = 100$ m, $\alpha = 2.1$, $R_B = 0.1$ bits, $\rho_0 = 1$, $M = (M_x, M_z) = (12, 12)$, $M_O = \{16, 36\}$, $W = (W_x, W_z)\lambda^2 = (2, 2)\lambda^2$, and $\sigma_B^2 = \sigma_W^2 = -90$ dBm. We also assume the carrier frequency f_c at 2.4 GHz, hence, $\lambda = 0.125$ m. Furthermore, we benchmark the performance against a conventional RIS with optimized phases and the same physical size as the FRIS, where \hat{M} denotes the number of reflecting elements.

Fig. 2 depicts the OP performance as a function of the transmit power P_A for different numbers of reflecting elements

Fig. 3. COP versus transmit power P_A for different μ .

Fig. 4. Success probability versus transmit power P_A for different number of fluid elements M_O .

in FRIS and conventional RIS, denoted by M_O and \hat{M} , respectively. The close agreement between the simulation and analytical curves confirms the accuracy of the derived expressions. As expected, the OP decreases monotonically with P_A , since higher transmit power improves the SNR at Bob. Increasing the number of reflecting elements further enhances reliability, as larger surfaces provide stronger reflected signals and higher diversity gain. It is noteworthy that FRIS achieves a steeper OP reduction compared to RIS for the same number of elements. This performance gain arises from the fluid-based reconfiguration capability of FRIS, which enables adaptive selection of the most favorable subset of elements to maximize the cascaded Alice-FRIS-Bob link. In contrast, conventional RIS lacks such flexibility, thereby limiting its effectiveness in mitigating unfavorable fading conditions.

Fig. 3 shows the covertness outage probability P_{CO} as a function of the transmit power P_A for several threshold offsets μ (see 14). Consistent with the power-detector model, P_{CO} increases monotonically with P_A , since larger transmit power lowers the normalized threshold $\mu/(P_A L_{AF} L_{FB})$, making successful detection by Willie more probable. The parameter μ shifts the operating point; larger μ implies a higher threshold and thus delays the onset of outage to higher powers. In the Bob-centric configuration considered here, FRIS curves appear to the left of those for RIS, indicating higher COP at a given P_A , which is attributed to element selection/phasing that maximizes Bob's cascade but can also increase Willie's effective gain. It is noted that Willie-aware FRIS designs, e.g., penalized selection, would shift the FRIS curves rightward and thereby reduce COP.

Fig. 4 illustrates the success probability as a function of the transmit power P_A for both FRIS and conventional RIS under different numbers of reflecting elements. The success probability exhibits a unimodal trend: at low transmit powers, the link to Bob suffers from severe outage, resulting in negligible success probability. As P_A increases, channel reliability improves while Willie's detector remains ineffective, driving the success probability to its maximum. However, beyond a certain power level, Willie's detection becomes more reliable, which significantly reduces the success probability and yields the observed bell-shaped curves. When comparing the two architectures, FRIS consistently achieves higher success probability at lower transmit powers due to its element-selection capability, which strengthens the Alice–Bob channel while suppressing leakage to Willie. At very high transmit powers, however, the FRIS curves decay faster than those of conventional RIS, since the latter, optimized toward Bob without active selection, induces less unintentional alignment toward Willie. Furthermore, increasing the number of reflecting elements shifts the curves leftward and raises the peak value, demonstrating that larger surfaces are more power-efficient and provide a higher likelihood of successful covert communication.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper studied covert communication in the presence of a FRIS and compared its performance with that of a conventional RIS. A system model was developed in which Alice aims to communicate covertly with Bob while an adversary, Willie, attempts to detect the transmission. We derived a closed-form expression for the COP in terms of the FA and MD probabilities. Furthermore, we characterized the success probability under the optimal detection threshold, highlighting the trade-off between covertness and reliable communication. Our numerical results demonstrated that FRIS provides substantial advantages over conventional RIS in terms of enhancing reliability and covertness, especially at low-to-moderate transmit power regimes. The element-selection capability of FRIS enables stronger reinforcement of the legitimate Alice-to-Bob channel while suppressing leakage toward Willie, thereby reducing OP and improving the MD

performance. However, results also indicated that at very high transmit powers, conventional RIS may appear more robust in sustaining success probability, since FRIS's adaptive focusing can inadvertently enhance the signal leakage to Willie. This insight highlights a key power-dependent trade-off in FRIS-aided covert communication.

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